

Decoding Legal Evolution Examining the Impact of New Criminal Laws on India's Independence from British Legal Influences through a Linguistic Lens

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Abstract

Law is the means of maintaining harmony and order in society by protecting law abiders from criminals. The criminal codes are set in place to ensure citizens are not oppressed by other citizens and to enforce the control and rule of the king. During the 18th and 19th centuries, the kings were replaced by European imperialists across the globe, and India was ruled by the Britishers. As they overturned the heterogeneous monarchy, to establish complete political control, they made all the acts that were obstacles in maintaining their political and superior dominion as crime. Further, as they learned that the criminal codes in India were disorganized, they organized the law drawing from British legal philosophies to suit their rule. As India gained independence, all oppressive laws were amended but the criminal code, for the most part, maintained its original nature. The classification of crime, criminal justice administration, and the powers of judges and courts continued as in the times of Britishers. Thus, the current Indian government to remove the deep-rooted aftermath of imperial rule, has floated the new Criminal Codes to completely indigenize the law. Thus, this paper aims to examine whether the evolution of criminal codes of India post-independence has been able to remove the British influence.

Keywords Indian Criminal Laws, Post-Colonialism, British Influence, Legal Independence, Linguistic Pretense, Colonial Legacy.

Introduction

According to Salmon, law is the body of Principles recognised, and applied by the State in the Administration of Justice, whilst as per Rudolph Von Ihering's law definition. – "The form of the guarantee of conditions of life of society, assured by State's power of constraint. As you can see, the difference in the definition is the point of perspective, one from the side of the state and the other from the acceptance of society. As a matter of fact, in countries following democracy and especially representative democracies, the law ought to reflect the ideals of the state. A philosophy that ultimately boils down to self-governance, or Swarj, as demanded by our freedom fighters from the imperialists. However, after attaining freedom the first torchbearer of the Swaraj government, kept on continuing the law made by the imperialist with certain editions and deletions made time and again to suit the need of the hour, but never were the transformed or re-drafted for India, by Indians to represent the principles of Indians and the society they wish to achieve. This need was long pending to be fulfilled, as the current government came into power, it always has preached governance for India, favouring India and developing India. Thereby, washing off the cast of aftermaths of imperial rule. In the conquest of delivering true Swaraj, the current government has recently introduced the Bhartiya Nyaya Sanhita Bill, which aims to not just replace but re-appeal the exiting Indian Penal Code of 1860. The bill so introduced in the parliament is still under consideration and discussion. At this very stage, it sparked debate, confusion, and battle. Surprisingly, the debate is not on the provisos it contained but on whether there was any need for this or if it was just the current government, yet another trick to rebrand the old thing in front of the public. Thus, the researcher aims, through this study, to analyse the fruitfulness of the current bills introduced by the government of India and analyse the possible outcomes.

Objective of study

1. To critically analyse the laws that are being (re)defined for Indian Citizens
2. To examine the changes under the new criminal legislation vis-a-vis existing British legal regime
3. To analyse whether they are suitable for Indians following the Theory of Volksgeist

Review of Literature

1. *Critical Analysis of The Bharatiya Nyaya Sanhita Bill 2023 With Special Regard to Laws Concerning Rape and Unnatural Offences by Archana Gupta*Ashim Nanda*¹ (Archana Gupta), in this Research article, the author has scrutinized the whole act and highlighted that despite the new amendments the government has still failed to address certain considerations of modern society, leaving out some sections of society and missed animals. The rights of the LGBTQ+ community and the rampant crimes against domestic animals or stray animals have yet again been left out of the purview and protection of the law and state.

2. *The Bhartiya Nyaya Sanhita, 2023: Analysing the proposed replacement to the Indian Penal Code, 1860 (1/3) by Ankoosh Mehta, Ankoosh Mehta and others*² (Ankoosh Mehta)- this research article, attempts to give an overview of the new crimes brought about by this bill and focuses on how the old crimes have been redefined. The authors in this research commend the policy markers for stricter laws in the field of cyber law and economic crimes, however, it questions the makers on their description of crimes against the state. This article highlights the vagueness of the wording and language of the bill and insists upon further clarifications and refinements at the government's end.

3. Karl Renner an Austrian jurist, focussed on viewing law as a tool for social control and engineering. He advocated for the use of law to foster social harmony, address social conflicts, and reduce inequalities. Renner underscored the role of legislation and legal institutions in shaping and reforming society, advocating for legal changes to achieve social justice and equality.

4. Roscoe Pound propogated a "sociological jurisprudence" approach, suggesting that law should be understood based on its societal impacts rather than just abstract principles. He believed that law should adapt to meet the evolving needs and values of society, emphasizing social welfare and justice. Pound emphasized the concept of "law in action," asserting that the effectiveness of the law should be evaluated based on its real-world consequences rather than just its formal provisions.

5. Leon Petrazycki a Russian legal theorist who highlighted the significance of psychology and sociology in comprehending the law. He introduced the concept of a "pure sociology of law," aiming to examine law as a social phenomenon without moral or philosophical considerations. Petrazycki stressed the importance of studying law within the context of social relationships and interactions, asserting that legal norms are influenced by social forces and cultural values.

Methodology

The research adopts a doctrinal approach, relying on existing laws and ethical principles to analyze their impact on societal norms. It employs a comprehensive methodology, integrating legal analysis with empirical data, statistics, and research from national and international sources. To ensure impartiality, the study utilizes primary, secondary, and tertiary sources, including constitutional documents, international agreements, journals, research reports, and literature.

Analysis

Redefining Old Crimes-

Since independence, contemporary governments have always tried to do away with the colonial laws that are no longer socially apt and legally relevant. Therefore, the Bhartiya Nyaya Sanhita has tried to redefine the old crimes. Numerous crimes have been redefined to either increase or decrease the ambit in the wake of suiting the needs of current society.

The offense of rape has been defined under section 63 "...A man is said to commit "rape" if he— (a) penetrates his penis, to any extent, into the vagina, mouth, urethra or anus of a woman or makes her do so with him or any other person; or (b) inserts, to any extent, any object or a part of the body, not being the penis, into the vagina, the urethra or anus of a woman or makes her do so with him or any other person; or (c) manipulates any part of the body of a woman to cause penetration into the vagina, urethra, anus or any part of body of such woman or makes her to do so with him or any other person; or (d) applies his mouth to the vagina, anus, urethra of a woman or makes her to do so with him or any

other person, under the circumstances falling under any of the following seven descriptions: — (i) against her will. (ii) without her consent. (iii) with her consent, when her consent has been obtained by putting her or any person in whom she is interested, in fear of death or of hurt....”³

This is the same definition as provided in IPC under section 375. the only difference over here is that in furtherance this section has enhanced the punishment for the crime. Similarly, crimes committed by police officers, armed forces, or hospitals have been penalised just the same way as under IPC 1860. There is no difference in the definition provided of this crime in BNS as against in IPC. It is also pertinent to note that it is keeping different forms of committing rape out of its ambit.

In the case of *Santhosh vs State of Kerala*, (*SANTHOSH vs the state of Kerala*) here, in this case, the accused had raped the victim by holding her thighs together and performing non- penetrative sex. the court had held that even though it was non-penetrative sex between the thighs it still account for rape. Despite this landmark judgment in 2016, it has not been incorporated into BNS. There are various forms of non-penetrative sex and sexual assaults other than disrobing and voyeurism.

Further, in the crimes of criminal force to assault or of voyeurism and disrobing women under sections 74-76, the offender has been made gender neutral however the victim continues to remain a woman. The *Bhartiya Nyaya Sanhita* (hereinafter referred to as BNS), thereby has increased the ambit of people who can be punished. It has done a good job of identifying the predators against women and realising gender neutrality in criminal acts. earlier in IPC the offender could only be a man, but with this change, the scope of penalisation has increased. But the victim remains the same.

In the case of organized crime, the inspiration has been drawn from the state's acts on organized crime. The nature and wordings have been highly drawn from MOCCA. Under section 109(1) it is defined as ... *“Any continuing unlawful activity including kidnapping, robbery, vehicle theft, extortion, land grabbing, contract killing, economic offenses, cyber- crimes having severe consequences, trafficking in people, drugs, illicit goods or services and weapons, human trafficking racket for prostitution or ransom by the effort of groups of individuals acting in concert, singly or jointly, either as a member of an organised crime syndicate or on behalf of such syndicate, by use of violence, the threat of violence, intimidation, coercion, corruption or related activities or other unlawful means to obtain direct or indirect, material benefit including a financial benefit, shall constitute organised crime”⁴* as promising it may seem, it contains a lot of issues-

a. The lack of differentiation between attempted and completed offenses is evident in Clause 109(2), which eliminates the distinction by prescribing the same penalties for both scenarios within organized crime. Previously, laws like MCOCA and GujCOCA differentiated between attempted and completed offenses by imposing varying penalties. Under Clause 109(2), individuals face the death penalty or life imprisonment if the offense results in a fatality, and a minimum of five years to life imprisonment otherwise. Notably, this clause does not necessitate a distinct mental state for causing death, potentially leading to individuals being sentenced to death irrespective of their knowledge or intent.

b. The absence of a requirement for knowledge or intent in facilitating organized crime is highlighted in Clause 109(3), which does not stipulate that individuals assisting or facilitating such crimes must possess knowledge or intent. In contrast to prior laws like MCOCA and GujCOCA, where knowledge of aiding in organized crime was essential for prosecution, Clause 109(3) could potentially penalize individuals who unknowingly aid in preparatory acts. For instance, an individual purchasing clothing for a group that later uses it for a robbery could be held accountable under this clause, even without awareness of their intentions.

c. Challenges arise with the clause concerning harbouring and concealing individuals involved in organized crime, as outlined in Clause 109(5). This clause criminalizes the act of harbouring or concealing individuals who have committed organized crime, with an additional provision penalizing those who believe their actions will encourage or assist such criminal activities. The provision's wording is ambiguous and could be interpreted as encompassing the act of harbouring or concealing someone who aids in organized crime. Moreover, the clause includes a provision exempting spouses of offenders from prosecution for harbouring or concealing, a provision lacking a clear rationale and not restricted to specific circumstances, thereby prompting inquiries into its necessity and equity.

A similar and unfortunate condition exists for the crime of sedition. The definition of sedition in IPC ... "[124A. Sedition.—Whoever by words, either spoken or written, or by signs, or by visible representation, or otherwise, brings or attempts to bring into hatred or contempt, or excites or attempts to excite disaffection towards, 11***the Government established by law in 12[India], 13***shall be punished with 14[imprisonment for life], to which fine may be added, or with imprisonment which may extend to three years, to which fine may be added, or with fine. Explanation 1.—The expression “disaffection” includes disloyalty and all feelings of enmity. Explanation 2.—Comments expressing disapprobation of the measures of the Government to obtain their alteration by lawful means, without exciting or attempting to excite hatred, contempt, or disaffection, do not constitute an offense under this section. Explanation 3.—Comments expressing disapprobation of the administrative or other action of the Government without exciting or attempting to excite hatred, contempt or disaffection, do not constitute an offense under this section.]”⁵

In the case of “Vombatkere v Union of India, (Vombatkere vs Union of India)order on 11 May 2022” while passing the judgment the Supreme Court had held that the central and state government should restrain the use of this section and restrain from filling FIRs under section 124A, in response to which the attorney general had assured the reconsideration being done by the government for the said section.

However, under BNS, the word “ sedition” has not been used, instead it has been reframed as acts against the government. “Whoever, purposely or knowingly, by words, either spoken or written, or by signs, or by visible representation, or by electronic communication or by use of financial mean, or otherwise, excites or attempts to excite, secession or armed rebellion or subversive activities, or encourages feelings of separatist activities or endangers sovereignty or unity and integrity of India; or indulges in or commits any such act shall be punished with imprisonment for life or with imprisonment which may extend to seven years and shall also be liable to fine.” Under clause 150, this definition is the sole reiteration of section 124a of the IPC, by just incorporating the new means of performinging seditious acts. (Ranjan) It is startling to know that, while presenting the BNS, the Home minister had mentioned that sedition has been removed. Yet again, the same things have been reserved for us with a different plating. This new definition without proper explanations or exceptions empowers the police and the state with unregulated might, to control public reactions and freedom of expression of people. This is because there are no explanations for the terms in this definition, nor any exhaustive or inclusive list of acts have been mentioned for better understanding, fruitful and practical exercising, and rightful implementation of this act.

Addition of New Crimes – along with redefining old crimes, the government has tried to introduce new crimes, to make society safer. The idea here was to also criminalise the acts, which were causing grave hurt, trauma, and nuisance in the society, however not properly governed by IPC or any other legislation for the protection of society and maintaining peace and harmony. Briefly, the following new crimes have been introduced-

sexual intercourse with false promise of promotion or marriage being rape- under clause 69 the act of intercourse based on getting consent for sexual intercourse on the belief that the other person shall marry or give promotion in the future has been termed as rape. This has been made following various judicial pronouncements. Here the fact of the matter lies in that the person after having sexual intercourse refuses to marry the woman or give a promotion. This clause which may seem like a relief briefly, puts many innocent lives in danger. On one hand, it gives women, an unfair advantage in society, considering that, youth in India now have a more sexually active life before marriage. There are various reasons why marriages may not happen eventually, thus it gives women an unfair advantage to use such sections and clauses against offenders, to fulfil their malicious aims. On the other hand, because, youth today in India have a rather active sexual life, such clauses shall give rise to numerous cases, where there is malicious prosecution, and numerous false cases shall be filed to torture men. This in turn shall result in furtherance of the taboo around sexual intercourse before marriage. It is also pertinent to note that, this clause has been added at the behest of the concept of “Consent.” To understand and highlight that consent is extremely important and it may be attained manipulatively by giving false promises of marriage or promotion. However, herein there is no explanation or illustration as to cases where this shall stand to be true. The section gives no safeguards to the alleged accusations. Although this clause has been added following various judicial pronouncements, the proof of whether the consent was out of free will or coerced shall be a big challenge in these cases.

Similarly, under clause 83, the BNS states that “... *Whoever takes or entices away any woman who is and whom he knows or has reason to believe to be the wife of any other man, with the intent that she may have illicit intercourse with any person, or conceals or detains with that intent any such woman, shall be punished with imprisonment of either description for a term which may extend to two years, or with fine, or with both.*” it is one

of the many controversial clauses of the bill. The fact that it shifts the complete burden of responsibility on the offender, and frees the woman, in case of a woman choosing to leave her husband, makes this section highly questionable and regressive. It is pertinent to note that earlier, adultery for a criminal offense that was later de-criminalised through judicial pronouncements. This section yet again, opened the window of adultery to becoming a crime again, with the burden of blame being completely on the offender. This undermines the consent of a woman to freely choose her life partner and step out of marriage, as such allegations can be conveniently put on the man she chooses to live with, leaving her spouse. It is also startling to note that this legislation has been made gender-neutral, by using the phrase "whoever." This also brings women under this ambit.

In recent times, there have been numerous incidents of mob lynching observed in various regions of India. These occurrences reflect the deep-seated social and political divisions within the country, often stemming from religious or caste disparities. The Indian Penal Code, specifically under clauses 101 and 115, addresses instances where a group of five or more individuals collectively commits murder based on factors such as race, caste, religion, gender, birthplace, language, personal beliefs, or other grounds. According to this provision, each member of such a group is subject to punishment, including the death penalty or life imprisonment, along with fines. This legal framework represents a progressive step towards fostering social and religious harmony in society. Notably, the legislation is inclusive and does not differentiate based on the gender of the offender or victim, thereby broadening the

scope of accountability. Although the term "mob lynching" is not explicitly mentioned in the law, a comprehensive analysis of the relevant sections suggests that such acts are considered a severe form of culpable homicide, falling under the categories of grievous hurt or murder. However, there is no distinct classification for mob lynching as a separate criminal offense, nor does the law address attempts to commit such acts. The current definition of this crime is vaguely worded, leading to potential ambiguities and varying interpretations in terms of enforcement and penalties.

Theft and related crimes- theft and robbery have been a part of IPC, however, their ambit was limited and many times, the implications were left to police interoperations. added to that, certain acts that may amount to theft were not included in the previous legislation.

Thus, under section 304 snatching has been made an offence, under the category of theft. Earlier snatching of movable property like gold chains, other forms of jewellery, or any other electronic gadgets such as phones, laptops, or even wallets and purses could not be prosecuted properly. However, with this new addition, snatching is now a new offence thereby filling the gap and grey area. It is pertinent to note that before BNS only the state government of Gujarat had recognized snatching as a theft and a separate crime, however with this legislation we achieved pan-India application.

Petty organized crimes- Section 110 of the Bhartiya Nyaya Sanhita introduces a novel classification termed "petty organized crime," which distinguishes it from traditional "organized crime." This particular provision sanctions any illicit activity that induces a sense of insecurity among the populace, typically linked with prevalent forms of organized crime carried out by organized criminal factions or gangs, including mobile groups. The section delineates instances of such offenses, such as various forms of theft, unauthorized ticket vending, and the unauthorized disclosure of public examination papers. In contrast to Section 109, Section 110 does not delineate the specific methodologies through which these crimes must be executed, such as through coercion or violence, nor does it necessitate the direct or indirect acquisition of material gains.

Nevertheless, certain apprehensions arise concerning Section 110. The phrase "any crime that causes general feelings of insecurity among citizens" is ambiguous and could potentially result in an excessively broad interpretation. While the section enumerates specific offenses, it also encompasses a catch-all provision for "other common forms of organized crime," thereby further complicating its ambit. Furthermore, Section 110 permits petty organized crime to be perpetrated by any "criminal group or gang," yet it neglects to furnish a precise definition of this terminology. Additionally, unlike Section 109, there exists no stipulation mandating that the crime be carried out by an organized crime syndicate with a documented history of chargesheets within the preceding decade.

Change of Punishments-

while as there has been a revamping of crimes, so have been punishments altered. BNS has tried to make the laws stricter and stronger to emphasis deterrence. This has been done in a two-fold manner-

Firstly, the concept of Minimum List of Crimes having Mandatory Minimum Punishment. Mandatory punishment has been introduced.

This means for a certain specified crime, already a minimum punishment has been specified. This means that the judge must award those minimum punishments, irrespective of and by not considering other influencing the award of punishments. These punishments are fundamentally stricter and stronger. Therefore, despite being the minimum or the lowest punishment that must be awarded, it is grave enough to cause deterrence. Additionally, since they are mandatory there is no scope for compound-ability, bail, or plea bargaining done to secure reduced punishments. Often people resort to plea for compundability of crime, which means they insist on converting the punishments into fines which would be of a huge amount but shall prevent the convict from going to jail. Further, often criminals were advised to accept their guilt to settle for a reduced punishment, but having these minimum mandatory punishments, does away with such tactics, helping the government establish the due fear in the minds of criminals.

SOURCE- SCC ONLINE

1	S. 99- Buying Child for Purposes of Prostitution, etc.
2	S. 105- Punishment For Culpable Homicide Not Amounting to Murder.
3	S. 111(2)(b)- Organised Crime.
4	S. 111(3)- Abetting, attempting etc. of an Organised Crime.
5	S. 111(4)- Being a member of Organised Crime.
6	S. 111(5)- Harboring a member of Organised Crime.
7	S. 111(6)- Possessing property derived from Organised Crime.
8	S. 111(7)- Possession of property on behalf of member of Organised Crime.
9	S. 112(2)- Petty Organised Crime
10	S. 113(2)(b)- Terrorist Act.
11	S. 113(3)- Abetting, attempting etc. of Terrorist Act.
12	S. 113(4)- Organising a camp for Terrorist Act.
13	S. 113(6)- Harboring any person who has committed any terrorist Act.
14	S. 117(3)- Voluntarily Causing Grievous Hurt resulting in permanent vegetative state
15	S. 118(2)- Voluntarily Causing Hurt or Grievous Hurt by Dangerous Weapons or Means.
16	S. 121(2)- Voluntarily Causing Hurt or Grievous Hurt to Deter Public Servant from His Duty.
17	S. 139(1)- Kidnapping or Maiming a Child for Purposes of Begging.
18	S. 139(2)- Kidnapping or Maiming a Child for Purposes of Begging.
19	S. 204- Personating A Public Servant
20	S. 303(2)- Theft.
21	310(3)- Dacoity.

22	314- Dishonest Misappropriation of Property
23	320- Dishonest or Fraudulent Removal or Concealment of Property To Prevent Distribution Among C

Furthermore, the BNS serves to increase the severity of penalties for existing criminal offenses. This includes the ability to impose minimum fines, longer prison sentences, life imprisonment, and even the death penalty for a wider range of crimes than previously permitted. The primary objective is to establish a strong deterrent effect on individuals with criminal inclinations within society. Additionally, the BNS introduces a mechanism for the rehabilitation of first-time offenders, aiming to prevent their association with more experienced criminals in correctional facilities. A novel approach introduced by the BNS is the concept of "Community Service" for minor offenses, which not only promotes restorative justice within the community but also aids in the reintegration of offenders into society.

By engaging offenders in projects that contribute positively to societal welfare, the system aims to foster a sense of belonging and purpose among them, thereby reducing the likelihood of repeat offenses. Moreover, community service initiatives facilitate the development of positive relationships between offenders and community members, breaking down barriers and stereotypes, and promoting mutual understanding and social cohesion. With this change, India joins the ranks of countries like the US, UK, Sweden and many other developed nations that provide for community services as a form of punishment. (Moti)

The above chart, depicts the crime rates in different countries of the world, with specific reference to murder, As it can be observed that, all these nations are the ones where law and order is dysfunctional. There are countries where the norms for murder are that strong. Thus, drawing from this comparison, it can be attributed that having stricter punishments is essential to enforce law and order in society. One another perspective that can draw over here is that the justice administration and law enforcement mechanism in these countries is poor, resulting in such rampant criminal activities, thus not only should the norms and punishments be strict the justice administration, the process of prosecution, and final penalisation must be robust and speedy to crack down such criminal activities.

Prominent Issues- The BNS, comes across as a promising attempt to revamp and do away with the shadow of colonialism, it unfortunately comes with similar or the same issues as we faced under IPC, 1860-

1. Gender Biasedness- all the crimes that have been described against the human body, especially that of sexual nature only sees women as the potential and vulnerable section of society that can be a victim. It fails to recognize the numerous gender identities that

are present in India. India as a country is now openly recognizing gender fluidity, people are no longer contained in binary genders of male and female. Further, a regressive approach is projected over here, considering only women or females can be victims. India in the recent past has across many instances of sexual assault or harassment of a man by woman, or man by man, or of a woman by woman. None of such acts are criminalised over here. as males under 18 are concerned they are protected under POCSO act, however, the rest of the population does not even have the vulnerability to get attacked, as per this new bill.

2.Vagueness- when Britishers ruled, India they often kept laws in favour of the elite and the language for purposefully kept vague for the British administration to exploit as much as they could. With the new bill, this idea of the ruling class being a ringmaster was expected to change, however, in the garb of making the laws all the stricter, the government has made the same mistake or mischief of keeping the laws vague. The description of crimes, lacks explanations, provisos, and proper definition of each ingredient that constitutes the crime. The language and wordings are redundant. For example, the words lunatic has been changed with mental illness, which literally and etymological have different meaning. Further the description of punishments, are not proper, there s mention of two or more punishments by using the word "or" and not "or and both."

3.Clause 4(b) highlights a problem in the Bhartiya Nyaya Sanhita (BNS) where some offenses carry the possibility of life imprisonment as a penalty, while aggravated forms of the same offense prescribe a whole life sentence. This creates inconsistency because both types of sentences end up being the same if "life imprisonment" always means a whole life sentence. For example, the punishment for rape can range from ten years to life imprisonment, while aggravated rape carries the same sentence but for the remainder of the offender's natural life. Similarly, murder can result in either life imprisonment or the death penalty, but if someone convicted of murder is already serving a life sentence, they receive another whole life sentence along with the death penalty. This leads to confusion and defeats the purpose of having stricter penalties for aggravated offense.

4.Other life forms left out of the bill are supposed to reflect the needs and wants of society and indigenous Indian values and perspectives on peaceful and harmonious society; however, it fails to cover in its ambit the other life forms apart from humans. India today being a youthful population that is aware and sensitive towards animals and nature, expects norms for animal rights as well. considering that fact, we have numerous instances of humans inflicting predatory behaviour and actions on stray animals, torturing them, beating them other forms of unnatural acts, etc., all of this has not been covered at all. Similarly, any harm and damage to the physical environment has not been covered by BNS. The gross violation of sustainability norms regarding rivers a forest has simply kept away from BNS's ambit. An argument in dense can be that for such activities, other legislations exist, however, this bill could have been a support strengthening those legislation, giving impetus and making such inhumane acts to be rightfully categorized as crimes against the environment and humanity.

Conclusion

It can be summarised that, in the many attempts of the current Indian government to bring back Bharat's real and true glory before being colonised, this is yet another bold attempt. Changing the basic penal legislation to suit the needs of the country, and to remove redundancy is brave. however, unfortunately, the fruits of these efforts seem sour prima facie. The IPC has been streamlined into lesser sections and there has been a change in the existing crimes. That forms the major part of the change, as the definition and the punishments have been enhanced. It feels like it is an upgrade to the existing IPC, which could have been brought about by certain amendments, because the lacunae of IPC, and the acts that were ignored by IPC, continue to exist. There are no norms for transgenders, animals, nature, or other sensitive and ignored issues of law. transgenders though an integral part of society are being governed by apart legislation that fails to provide them full protection, unlike other mainstream societies.

These fundamental laws aim to give comprehensive and wholistic governing norms for the whole of society, however, these laws are not in sync with the needs and wants of contemporary Indian society. Further, one of the deductions from the above analysis can comfortably be that the government has just given us the same product with different packaging and new tastemakers for rather more acceptability. For the want of acceptability, yes, the government has removed section 377 and the term sedition from this new law. it has focussed more on newer forms of cyber crimes and offered stricter punishments.

The hope that this bill brings to us is the enhanced punishments. It has been duly observed that in countries with severe punishments and judicial and law enforcement mechanisms coming heavily down on the criminals in countries i.e. Gulf Nations like Dubai, Kuwait, etc., the fear of the law is so much that it deters people from turning into offenders. Given the

current nature of the bills, it has rather to resulted in more confusion and numerous false and malicious trials. Numerous cases where the evidence will not be enough to fully establish the crime and the description is vague. Furthermore, it has reduced the scope of protection of innocent lives who are falsely framed. Since certain crime punishments are already set, it takes away the executive power of the judiciary to penalise offenders based on intellect and prudence, given the fact they are regarded as the most prudent minds in society.

In conclusion, all this did require a new bill and could have been sorted rather better by a criminal law amendment bill, and the fruitfulness of this shall depend upon the effectiveness of implementation.

**Suggestions
for the future
Study**

Based on the above research the following suggestions-

1. It is high time that rape laws be re defined and become gender neutral. The definition should not be restricted to only penetrative sex, but other means of sexual assault or harassment, by any of the gender binary, as well as non-binary. The definition for victim of rape should also be incorporating all genders.
2. This should be done in consonance with POCSO act, where anyone below 18 years is protected from both male and female gender, however it should also include non- binary genders.
3. The new crime of having sexual intercourse with false promise of getting married, is redundant and regressive approach , especially in the era where social norms around sexual intercourse are changing. As this section put men in the society on serious disadvantage, there must be proper explanation of situations that can be put under its ambit. This definition should rather be inclusive and exhaustive.
4. Similarly, the clause 83, is a dangerous clause and should be done removed, following various Supreme Court judgments, and decriminalization of redundant law adultery. As much family values must be protected so should be individual's consent to marriage. Thus, if at all the section is to be kept, it should be a civil, personal wrong and not a crime, while the onus being on the one who breaks and contravenes the conjugal duties and rights.
5. Additionally, under aggravated forms of grievous hurt an attempt is made to add offence of mob-lynching, but is dangerously poorly worded, leaving wide scope for false and malicious prosecution. The government instead should pass a separate act like the POCSO, where it defines and deals with Mob-lynching, and other sorts of public outrage. A separate at, giving thorough and explicit explanation so applicable situations, speedy trial as well as apt evidences that are necessary.
6. These changes shall render ineffective as there no change in procedure, or issuance of guild lines to the implementer i.e. the POLICE department. The police department, and norms so governing must be immediately update, modifies, or amended as the case maybe, for every specific law and clause mentioned din the new codes, ensure, just and fair and effective implementation.
7. Similarly, the procedural laws for these codes and limitation periods must be reduced, also curtailing the powers of judged to grant innumerable adjournments, and extensions for court proceedings, to render these amendments viable and effective.

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